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Conservation And Preservation Of Stone Monument And Its Archaeological Importance Among Okpuje In Nsukk

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ABSTRACT

The paper is concern about the conservation and preservation of stone monument and its archaeological significance among Okpuje in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. It is pertinent to note that for any conservation to succeed the public need to be adequately informed and educated about the resources, so until the public is made to show interest in the conservation and preservation, laws and regulations will always remain ineffective. The paper sought to find out the rationale for conservation of these heritages stone monuments in sacred landscape as an aspect of our archaeological resources to be preserved. The use of functional theory guided the study. The findings revealed that stone monument as an aspect of our natural and cultural heritage created in the historic past and present enable people in the community to cope with the challenges of the environment and survive. The research made use of primary and secondary sources. The study was based on descriptive analysis. Observation, interview and focused group discussion were the data gathering techniques. Books, journal and public library and internet materials were relied upon for secondary data so as to complement data derived from primary sources

Keywords: Conservation, Preservation, Stone, Monument, Archaeological importance.

INTRODUCTION

Stones are natural resources mankind has been using for various purposes from archaeological past to ethnographic present. Man used stone during the oldowan, Acheulian and Aterian period to make different tools for various purposes during the early stage of his history (Ogundele 2014:112).

Traditionally, stone monument in nsukka in Igboland are referred to as Ugwu Okpuje, it is conserved and preserved among Okpuje in Nsukka because of its spiritual significance as symbolic objects imbued with social and natural powers. This stone monument in their location served as a place for religious worship; ceremonial centers and ritual sacrifices to the gods of the land. Apart from its monumental functions, stones are also used for building of houses, construction of road and grinding of food items like maize, melon, pepper and so on. The conservation and preservation of stone monument have receive little or no attention by the people in the recent time as a result of deterioration of those stones caused by environmental factors, like rain, water, degradation of sites caused by human agents and Christianity that have affected people's beliefs in places of worship where the stone monument are located, as well as vandalism of archaeological sites. Berti (2016) observes that the knowledge of the technique of the past and natural environment of stones is a key to sustainable preservation of this heritage.

Significantly, conservation practices are very necessary to indigenious communities as they ensure the sustainability of natural and cultural resources in order to guarantee their availability for generation yet

unborn. For any conservation law to succeed therefore, the public need to be adequately educated about the resources; and until the public is made to show interest in the conservation, preservation and protection of resources, laws and regulations which guide the natural and cultural landscape will always remain ineffective because the motives behind such conservation law should aim at fostering self-esteem, economic and tourism development, community relation and/ or integration and national unity. Conservation of stone monument can be seen as a form of managing cultural resource and the expansion of the scope of History and Archaeology as a discipline in which its status as a purely academic discipline is modified bringing in the conservation, preservation of its heritage thereby making it relevant to the aspirations of the general public (Folorunsho, 1998).

Ozturk (1992) opines that an understanding of the terrapins (culture, environment, science and mechanism) for stone heritage, sustainable preservation could be achieved. Conservation is a means by which natural and cultural heritage are properly protected from decay and damage. (Edet 1990) while Eluyemi (2002:2) sees preservation as the promotion of cultural property whether of concrete or non-concrete nature past and present. It includes also documentation, identification, registration and proper storage of cultural objects whether in private hand or museum.

Critically, stone monument which constitutes natural and cultural objects created by nature or modified by man is very vital to be preserved as an aspect of the people's cultures and values. It is pertinent to note that creating and maintaining conducive environment for these stone monument in cultural landscape will enhance their protection and make the object to continue to function effectively and efficiently. Therefore there is the need to conserve and preserve this stone monument as fundamental basis for traditional religious worship where admirers and adherents visit for their varied spiritual needs (Okonkwo and Eyisa: 2016). It should be noted that this stone monument in landscape has been abandoned because of Christianity and the destruction of archaeological sites. These stones constitute aspect of our archaeological and ethnographic resources that have to be properly conserved and managed to avoid deterioration and decay. The use of functionalist theory is very relevant in this study as Malinowski's assumed that all natural and cultural objects constitute useful part of the society where they occur. This calls for proper conservation and preservation because these stones are the symbolic expression of people's pattern of belief and behavior, attitudes and social structure. They perform useful function to meet the need of the community and the people also derive benefits from their existence. It is against this background that the paper attempts to examine conservation and preservation of stone monument and its archaeological and historical importance among Okpuje in Nsukka.

Statement of the Problem

The importance of stone monument in archaeology and ethnographic studies cannot be overemphasized but its conservation and preservation seem to be neglected especially among Okpuje and various communities in Nigeria. Stone objects have been used in Nigeria since Acheulian time. For instance in Nok, and Igboukwu, stone hand axes, cleaver, and pick were recovered (Okonkwo and Ibeanu 2016). This could not have been possible without proper preservation in the environment. Stone objects during pre-colonial Nigeria were conserved and preserved as sacred in royal palaces of tribal kings, among the Igbo and Yoruba, by heads of families, priest of shrine and deities for ritual sacrifice and religious purposes (Fasuyi 1975). The advent of colonialism, Christianity, environmental degradation and vandalism of archaeological sites had affected conservation and preservation of stone monuments and importance placed on them by various communities in Nigeria.

Maurice (2010) defined monument as any object created in honour of someone or to commemorate an important event. It also involves something a community considers important in their history. Therefore, the paper attempts to draw the attention of the public and fill the gap by examining conservation and preservation of stone monument and its archaeological importance among Okpuje Community in Nsukka area.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine conservation and preservation of stone monument and its archaeological importance among Okpuje in Nsukka. Specifically the objectives of the study include:

1. To find out the meaning and techniques of conservation and preservation of stone monument.
2. To examine how stone monument is conserved and preserved in sacred landscape as objects of ritual and religious worship.
3. To ascertain the rationale for stone monument conservation and preservation as aspect of our archaeological resources.

Significance of the Study

The conservation and preservation of stone monument as objects and places of religious worship, ceremonial centre and ritual sacrifices is as old as Okpuje but there is no written document concerning how these stones are conserved and preserved in the study area.

This study would be significant to Okpuje people, Igbo land, and Nigeria as it will give more insight into the knowledge, understanding and appreciation of the need to preserve and conserve their natural and cultural heritage for posterity. It will awaken the people's interest on the aspect of their heritage that embodies on ceremonies and festivals associated with stone monument. It will also help the people to know and gain knowledge about the use of stone in antiquity. And will also serve as a reference point to students of History, Archaeology and tourism and other disciplines who would like to embark on further researches in the area.

Conceptual Clarification of Conservation and Preservation

The terms conservation and preservation are sometimes used interchangeably because both concepts have similar connotations, in that their major concern is to keep objects in question away from destruction, harm and decay (Okpoko 2011). Edet (1990) defines conservation as a means by which cultural property are properly protected from damage. Conservation tries to create a conducive environment by introducing something to keep an object intact away from harm. Eluyemi (2002) viewed preservation as the promotion of object whether of concrete and non-concrete nature, past and present. It also includes documentation, identification, registration and storage.

Preservation on the other hand, tries to maintain the environment created by nature in order to also keep such object intact. Conservation can also be seen as a scientifically informed discipline which is guided by general principles as well as by a growing body of written information (Okpoko 2011). Conservation was only limited to repair or disguise of damages of past materials and was usually carried out by the artists and artisans who were experienced in making the kinds of objects they repaired; but today, conservation has become more sophisticated and a science in the whole world. He also notes further that the word 'conservation' is an all-encompassing term which includes not only the restoration of works of man or nature that have been damaged, but also the preservation of these works through proper understanding of the best means for a long-term care. Berti (2016) rightly points out that the knowledge of techniques of the past and natural environment of the stone are keys to sustainable preservation.

According to Ige (2005), conservation as a concept evolved and developed from the appreciative efforts of the Western World. They focuses their attention on individual homes/buildings, sites and monuments of Archaeological and historical importance. For instance, in 1926, President Rockefeller of the United States of America made a decision to restore colonial buildings of old Sturbridge village, Mystic village in Connecticut and old Sedum in the state of North Carolina, and many others. These monuments or ancient structures, having been restored, later became useful research centers in America (Ige 2005).

In the 1930s, the American government also made some laudable efforts in identifying, recording and documenting buildings that were culturally significant to American history. This compilation was in the form of a National Register which later became an important tool that assisted the country in the identification, conservation and protection of physical remains of American cultural heritage. Similarly, Jegede (1996) asserts Nigeria commitments in the conservation, preservation of its cultural properties. This was based on the following reasons:

- i. The colonial government's awareness of large amount of Archaeological materials and other works of art that abound in the country, and the 1897 Punitive British Expedition of Benin.

ii. The high prices and the aesthetic attractions that those Nigerian archaeological materials and other works of art command in Europe.

iii. The unscrupulous western exploitation of loopholes due to porosity of Nigerian territorial boundaries. (Jegede,1996).

These reasons however, prompted the Nigerian government to come out with legislation prohibiting the export of ancient works of art without government's permission. However, prior to this development, the practice of Archaeology in Nigeria was more academic and research oriented, emphasizing only excavation and retrieval of data with the conservation, preservation and protection of archaeological sites receiving little or no attention. In fact, there was hardly any rescue work; and archaeological sites were being excavated primarily for academic purposes rather than because they were threatened. Publications were at that time only based on excavations reports while the practical issues of conservation in the country were hardly addressed even though the 1979 act had acknowledged that the conservation, preservation and protection of archaeological materials is important. However, it is sad to note here that the above scenario was as a result of lack of public education regarding conservation, preservation and protection of archaeological materials in the country. (Ige 2005).

For any conservation law to succeed therefore, the public need to be adequately educated about the resources; and until the public is made to show interest in the conservation, preservation and protection of resources, laws and regulations which guide the natural and cultural landscape will always remain ineffective because the motives behind such conservation law should aim at fostering self-esteem, economic and tourism development, community relation and/ or integration and national unity. Conservation of stone heritage can be seen as a form of managing cultural resource and the expansion of the scope of archaeology as a discipline in which its status as a purely academic discipline is modified bringing in the conservation, preservation of its heritage thereby making it relevant to the aspirations of the general public (Folorunso,1998).

Thus the history of conservation in the world has never been static. It has progressively evolved: and in the course of this evolution, various changes took place, these changes and developments had in most cases subsequently affected the manner and method in which conservation efforts were carried out.

Monuments

According to UNESCO (1970) in Maurice (2010), Monuments are unique works with outstanding universal value from the point of view of history or science. Monuments point to civilization and enhance respect for creativity. A monument is also any object created in honour of someone or to commemorate an important event. Thus monument develops from something that a community considers important in their life history like Ugwu Okpuje which the people of Okpuje venerate because of its spiritual importance to the people as a place for religious worship. In the words of Maurice (2010) again monuments are centre of attraction for tourists. Apart from their importance as memorabilia, a monument is also often used in an ornamental sense to beautify the town or neighborhood.

We have numerous monuments across the world for example Great Wall of China, Berlin wall and so on. In Nigeria we have the statue of the Late Chief Obafemi Awolowo at Allen Round about in Ikeja Lagos, cool camp riot of Enugu new market junction Enugu and many others.

According to Okpoko and Okpoko (2002), there are more than sixty three historic monuments declared by National Commission for Museum and Monuments in Nigeria (NCMM). These monuments include buildings of historical and architectural interest. They are ancient city walls and boundary mounds as well as cemeteries, also included are the historical building and compound at Keffin. Madaki, in Bauchi State, Ilojo Bar in Lagos State, Omo-Ukwu temple Abia State, Oshun shrine at Oshogbo Osun State, statutes and 19th century kings and paramount rulers like William Dappa Pepple (1886) and King Ockiya and Nembe (1876) and so on. (Okpoko and Okpoko 2002) They are conserved for their historical and archaeological values.

Techniques for Conservation of Stone

True preservation means more than just conserving an individual monument or building: it includes the preservation of the sacred landscape around a building, sacred stones, shrines, ceremonial places of

worship, the contextual archaeological site, heritage stones and the artifacts that have been excavated from sites as well as the conservation and protection of artifacts that remains in sites. (Folorunso, 1996) As Okpoko (2011) points out also that the conservation techniques of, for instance, stone are different from the conservation of stone objects. This is because; there are features that are always considered which include:

- i. A detailed pathological examination of the stone to show the state of the stone and its mineral condition.
- ii. Analysis of the content of the stone to determine the nature of salt in the stone through the use of X-ray diffraction.
- iii. Examination of the causes of damage on the stone object.

The conservation of the above features is very imperative because if the cause of previous damage is not known, conservation of the stone object may still be carried out but only for the stone to begin to show signs of deterioration and damage again just some few weeks or months later.

After the extent of damage has been determined, the process of cleaning with water now follows so as to remove old dirt including obstinate dirt which could not be removed by brushing. Thereafter, preservation treatment is then carried out on the stone object. This is done by applying paint on the subject.

Other conservation techniques used in the conservation of objects like wood, textiles, and metals include the use of consolidates, resins, waxes, steaming, impregnation, and smoking. All these materials whether organic or inorganic, the relevance of the whole exercise is that it “help in prolonging or lengthening the lives of objects and monuments” (Hudson, 1977 in (Okpoko 2011).

Rationale for Conservation and Preservation of Stone Monuments

The rationale and/or relevance of conservation and preservation of stone monument cannot be wished away (Scholars of Archaeology and Tourism). This is because of the much importance attached to it by many communities.

The need for conservation and preservation of stone monument seem important because the past is not dead; it is alive in our nation’s prehistoric and historic sites readily to reveal it to those who seek its knowledge and counsel (Jegade 1996).

Traditionally, this stone monument seen as sacred among the people serves as places of sacrifice should be kept in conducive environment. From the laws of motion there is evidence of worship at natural sites as well as sites made for ceremonial and ritual purpose. The prehistory of most ancient civilizations shows that people honour stones and other natural objects which became the object of established cults. Okpuje people that honour Ugwu Okpuje are not left out in this engagement as the stone monument becomes part and parcel of their cultural adornment. During festival, people pay homage to Ugwu Okpuje as place of ritual, sacrifice to commemorate the festive events. The reconstruction of history depends on the preservation of archaeological materials/evidence. The amount of evidence to be preserved depends on the conditions it has been exposed to and ability of archaeologist to recover it. Data that lie in the ground but cannot be recovered by an archaeologist are for practical purposes unpreserved. (Andah and Okpoko 1999, Dada and Orie 2014, Ogundele 2014).

Ibeanu (2000) cited in Okonkwo and Ibeanu (2016) notes the use of a stone anvil and hammer by Ugwogu blacksmiths in Uturu Okigwe. Okonkwo (2004) points out that in Sukur Kingdom, Adamawa State, there are 18th century grinding stones. Archaeologists have also observed the use of grinding stones among the people of Okpuje in Nsukka.

Stone artifacts have been produced in Nigeria since the Acheulian period. In the forest zone of South Eastern Nigeria a stone tool factory site was discovered in 1977 at Ugwuele – Uturu Okigwe (Ibeanu 2000 cited in Okonkwo and Ibeanu 2016). Many of these stone tools found in archaeological sites have been dated. This point to the need to continue to preserve these stones objects either for archaeological or ethnographic evidence among Nigerians.

Brief Account of Study Area

Okpuje is a town that is located at the north-west end of Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. It is on the trunk B road leading from Nsukka to Idah in Kogi State. At her Northern end, Okpuje has a common boundary with Ibagwa Agu in Nsukka Local Government Area; in the south, Orobo-Abbi in Uzo-uwani Local Government Area of Enugu State and in the west, Avurugo and Ugwaka in Kogi State. It is situated on a friendly land scope which is straddled, somehow, by two hills, one at the north and the other at the south, extending to the western part of the town. (Eze 2005)

Economy

The primary occupation of Okpuje is farming. This can be attributed to the large expanse of agricultural land on which it is situated. A lot of farm crops such as yams of various species, cocoa, yam, cassava, (for which the people are great garri producers), melon, maize, beans and et c are produced in the community. (Ogbobe, 2020).

Traditionally, a man is adjudged rich in okpuje based on the abundance of agricultural crops he possesses by traditional standards. Wealth in itself confers honour and dignity. Consequently, people strive to be wealthy and since an individual, working alone can hardly acquire wealth, it makes people to marry as many wives as they could. Many children are born and large scale farming is practiced. More hands, more wealth and greater recognition are achieved.

Religion

Okpuje people are deeply religious. They believe in the existence of Supreme Being called Ezechitoke Abiama (God the creator) who is the source of life. Atama Gabriel (2020) points out that apart from the main God, there is also a belief in a personal god called “chi” to which sacrifices are offered during festivals to commemorate the event. Furthermore, there is a belief in a pantheon of deities like Ugwu–Okpuje, Asama, Ahimuze and Obata and sacred stones. The chief priest called Atama is in charge of the deities and ritual sacrifice. It is pertinent to note that Christianity and western education have impacted so much on the traditional religion of Okpuje -Nsukka communities that most of them today are Christians of various denominations.

Political Life

The administrative set up of Okpuje as Ugwu Christopher notes comprises the elders and Ama-title holders. The elders are in charge of administering civil duties in villages and they also handle minor criminal disputes.

The council of Ama-title holders is in charge of handling cases which the elders could not settle. They serve as the final court of appeal. This council also deals directly with serious criminal cases. In serious cases of sacrilege such as disclosing the secrets of masquerade to a woman, the culprit is tried and fined by the general council. Other cases such as witchcraft and poisoning are settled by drinking of a liquid concoction from a tree called “Ohachi”. The belief is that the innocent would vomit the whole substance and live while the guilty shall die. The highest penalty that can be given is banishment. The Igwe-in-council is the paramount ruler while the Onyishi and representatives of each community form the leaders of the community.(Eze Emmanuel 2020).

Theoretical justification

The need to preserve and conserve stone monument among Okpuje, in Nsukka can be best explained through functionalist theory as enunciated by Bronislaw, Malinowski (1884-1942). Functionalist emphasize that society consist of inter related parts which work for the integration and stability of the whole system. Malinowski’s functionalism assumed that all cultural objects (trait) are useful part of the society where they occur. In other words, these stone monument are expressed in the people pattern of behavior, belief attitudes and social structure, perform a function within the society they occur. These stone and stone objects exist to meet the needs of human society. It provides cohesion in the social order by promoting a sense of belonging Durkheim (1897) argues that preservation is capable of promoting consciousness in terms of unity. Tangible objects are man’s physical ingenious products which can be touched and seen such as stone, wooden objects, grain foods, and iron furnace and so on. Artifacts which

refer to those objects made and used by man to cope with the challenges of the environment perform useful functions to the society. There is the need therefore for preservation and conservation of these stone objects because of their utilitarian values to human societies.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings and Discussion

The findings revealed that conservation and preservation of stone monument in sacred landscape among Okpuje is very vital as it is rooted in their tradition of ritual sacrifice and religious worship. It revealed that the various communities that made up Okpuje in pre-historic time preserved and conserved these stones in shrine, deities and places of Chiefs and Eze Okpuje as symbolic objects imbued with natural and spiritual power and by the priests who are the custodian of these shrines and deities for ritual sacrifice.

Traditional festivals like onunu ritual sacrifices were made to the gods on these stones by sprinkling the blood of animals like goat, fowls on this stone monument to appease the gods of the land. People are forced to swear at the shrine or deities using these stones, for committing one sacrilegious offence or the other. This made the Ugwu Okpuje to be feared and respected by the people.

The findings also revealed that the people of Okpuje especially women use these stones apart from the monumental function, for grinding food items such as pepper, melon, maize. This is in agreement with Okonkwo (2004) who notes that in Sukur Kingdom, Adamawa State, there are 18th century grinding stones. These stones are also used in the building of houses like the Eze Okpuje's house which was built with stone.

The importance of stones dates back to antiquity, archaeological findings in Nok and Igboukwu, revealed the use of these stone objects for making various tools which were found in archaeological sites.

Stones are natural resources used by man for various purposes. Man uses stone for making different type of tools, for various purposes during the early stages of their history. According to Uguru Gabriel, (2020) the custodian of Ugwu Okpuje deity, notes the stone which is called Nkpume in native language that surround the deity in the historic past were preserved and use for different sacrifices. The people of Okpuje visit the deity during festival or when the occasion demand to worship there and pour libation to the gods of their ancestors. During Onunu festival, people from far and near gather at the place to commemorate the event with different ritual sacrifice performed at the site.

The people had always take the deity very serious because people go there to worship and sacrifice to their gods which they believe are their provider, in time of needs and their protector. Eze Emmanuel (2020) said that apart from religious ritual and ceremonies surrounding the shrine, monument stone were used by the people before the advent of modern grinder to grind different food items by the women which we can see today in various remote villages at Agu Okpuje especially among the people who cannot afford the modern grinding machine. This actually made the people to appreciate and value them as part of their cultural heritage. Stones are used for building houses from the pre-historic time to the present. The house of Eze Okpuje along Okpuje Idah road was built with stone. In this respect we can see the need to preserve and conserve stones as they play vital role in the life of the people. It adds to their value system. However in the context of history and archaeology, early men used stone to make various tools which helped them to adapt and survive in their environment. Such early men like Australopithecus Africanus, Robustus, Homo habilis, and Homo erectus and so on used stones to kill animals for food, even in the ancient time. This shows that man has been using stones from archaeological past to ethnographic present.

At this juncture, we can see that conservation tends to affect all aspects of the environment. For instance, in many communities in Nigeria certain forest like Ugwu Okpuje is designated as shrine. These forests are in effect considered protected and reserved areas. These protected forests have multiple functions because they also influence other elements of the environment such as land use and management.

However, innovations, environmental degradation, vandalism of sites and modern values have eroded the use of these stones which the paper sought to draw attention of our people on the need to continue to preserve and conserve this stone monument.

CONCLUSION

The current state of stone monuments in our landscape among Okpuje in Nsukka calls for urgent attention in order to preserve and conserve them as they play vital role in the people's lives. Ozturk (1992:79) states that it is only through a complete understanding of terrain, culture, environment for stone heritage that sustainable preservation could be achieved.

Okpuje as a community from time immemorial significantly was associated with the worship of traditional gods which reflect their religious life and belief system. These stones in the sacred landscape were seen as symbolic spiritual place of worship where the people, visit to accomplish their traditional religious obligation and need. The shrine stone is an integral aspect of their traditional belief system and should be kept in conducive environment to avoid decay and damage. The existence of these sacred stones has been threatened by the environment, rain water, temperature etc. as well as Christianity thereby resulting in the relegation of indigenous mode of worship. To this day, the effect is still been felt in the religious life of the people among Nigeria. If given needed attention, stone monument can contribute in the development of religious tourism.

The importance of conservation of stone as archaeological resources in archaeological sites cannot be over emphasized. The early man use stone to make tools in order to cope and survive the challenges of the environment as well as dating of these sites have been determined by archaeologist use of stone. Therefore, there is need for continued conservation and preservation of these stones monument because of its benefits to the people of Okpuje and its archaeological importance to the general public.

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